

White Collar Crimes in Bangladesh, Its Causes and Negative Impacts: An Analysis Based on Legal Framework

Tahmina Akter

Undergraduate Student (12th Semester), Dept. of Law, Daffodil International University, Dhaka-1207, Bangladesh.

ABSTRACT

White collar crime poses a major threat for the country, the nation, and the general public. This is a monetarily persuaded crime done to get or try not to lose cash, property, administrations, or to get an individual or business advantage. It incorporates peaceful crime done in business circumstances to acquire cash. Rather than being another and advancing field of criminology, white-collar guiltiness has been predominantly common all through each area of the country in light of its extremely recognized highlights. These crimes are consuming inquiries in the period of present world circumstances. White-collar crime is continually advancing, incorporating a wide assortment of crimes, and having exceptional qualities that recognize it from savage and customary vandalism-related misdemeanors. Every country of the world is attempting to secure white-collar crime for the good foundation of the state. Regarding developing countries like Bangladesh, white-collar crime isn't notable yet. Besides, white-collar crimes are discouraged in Bangladesh and it is one of the significant issues in Bangladesh. The white-collar criminals similar to the heads of their particular fields, regularly keep themselves in the background. This existing paper tries to look at the contemporary issues as to white-collar crime in Bangladesh along with its causes, contributing factors, and the negative impacts of white-collar crime in Bangladesh. Moreover, the paper suggests few recommendations in order to prevent the white collar crimes from the society. The paper makes use of secondary data i.e. books, journals, newspaper articles, different national and international law reports, Acts etc.

Keywords: Bangladesh, Corruption, Criminology, White Collar Crime, Impacts.

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INTRODUCTION

Currently, white-collar crime is a terrible type of crime not only in Bangladesh but also the other countries of the world. Many people in developing countries like Bangladesh still do not know properly about white-collar crime. Although this crime is committed by the upper-class people, in most cases it is seen that the common people have to suffer for this crime. The idea of white collar crime has consistently been a marvel after colonization and industrialization in the eighteenth century. Yet, before Professor Sutherland, no crime analysts utilized this term or took the idea of white-collar crime with regards to criminology. A white collar criminal has a place with the upper financial class who abuses the principles for the monetary increase while playing out his expert obligations. White-collar crime is likewise done by the experts by utilizing the impact of his companion gatherings [1]. The introduction of white collar crime was a somewhat new issue to criminology around then. Bangladesh feels the quintessence of legal provisions for the anticipation of white collar crimes since numerous years prior. There has been a propensity to picture that lower-class people are bound to perpetrate crime, giving a deceptive thought that high society people are liberated from crimes. Yet, the act of crime and defilement by the world-class are normal and pointed every once in a while. The term 'white-collar crime' has been in successive use in the literature of American Criminology since December 1939 to demonstrate the act of dishonesty and defilement of the exceptionally positioned people. In December 1939 Edwin H. Sutherland utilized the term 'white-collar crime' in his official location before the American Sociological Society. The term was contended to be questionable and dubious, as there was no authority or legitimate definition. Sutherland utilized 'white-collar crime' as the title for his comments. He examined the issues identifying with white-collar crime' and later on, explained a considerable lot of its implications [2].

Historical Background of White Collar Crime

The genesis of white-collar crime isn't unreasonably old. The term white-collar crime traces all the way back to 1939. As said before Professor Edwin Hardin Sutherland was quick to coin the term, and conjecture white-collar criminals ascribed various qualities and thought processes than commonplace road criminals. Professor Sutherland initially introduced his hypothesis in a location to the American Sociological Society in the endeavor to examine two

fields, crime, and high society, which had no past exact connection. He reacted to those reactions in his article "Is 'White Collar Crime,' crime?" Published in 1945. He published a snare-length study "White Collar Crime" in 1949, where he gathered the information which he gathered during numerous years of research. He deliberately introduced his arguments and examined the ramifications of the theory [3]. Sutherland in 1949, published his well eminent classic book named "White-Collar Crime". Prior to that, Sutherland featured orderly research into the criminal act of the elites after the presence of the main version of his "Criminology" in 1924. In the second (in 1934) and third release (in 1939), he changed the title of the book (Principles of Criminology) and subsumed dispersed remarks on White Collar Crime [4]. Be that as it may, his 1939 official location was his first efficient definition of the term, which was exposed to the analysis of various quarters. White collar crimes contrast from the crimes carried out by criminal organizations. This differentiation could be founded on the degree of assumed decency. On the off chance that an individual, who has a place with a decent class of society and has some level of good standing, sells disgraceful products, he is perpetrating a white-collar crime. Yet, on the off chance that a gathering of people obscure to their casualties, sell the very sort of trashy products that would not be a white-collar crime.

Sutherland noticed that in his time, under two percent of the people perpetrated to penitentiaries in a year have a place with the privileged. His objective was to demonstrate a connection between cash; societal position and probability of going to prison are poor, "Authentic" criminals, regardless of endeavors to get serious about corporate crime. Other monetary laws were passed in the years preceding Sutherland's examinations remembering antitrust laws for the 1920s and social government assistance laws in the 1930s. After Depression, people put it all on the line to remake their monetary security and it is hypothesized that this drove numerous diligent employees who felt they were come up short on to exploit their positions. Notwithstanding the incredible lengths Sutherland went to portray precisely what he ordered as white-collar crime, the clearness of the subject was, is still rather expansive and uncertain.

White Collar Crime: General Meaning and Concept

White collar crime can be characterized from numerous points of view. It has been characterized ascribe carried out by one of good or high economic wellbeing or in the course of one's occupation, as a crime that includes double-dealing or a breach of trust, as peaceful crime embraced for individual addition, as a crime that involves a blend of these components, and essentially as a business crime. The idea of "white-collar crime" discovered its place in criminology for the first time in 1941 when sociologist and criminologist Edwin Hardin Sutherland published his research paper on white-collar criminality in the American Sociological Review [5]. He characterized the white-collar crime as a "crime committed by persons of respectability and high social status in course of their occupation".

According to Encyclopedia, 'White-collar crime is financially motivated nonviolent crime committed for illegal monetary gain'. Sir water Reckless, an eminent American criminologist suggests that White Collar Crime represents the offenses of businessmen who are in a position to determine the policies and activities of the business. Barnes and Teeters quoted Lord Acton who said, "Power tends to corrupt and absolute power tends to corrupt absolutely". Whatever citizens of a particular community become apathetic to the working of their government, grafts, corruption, and alliance between public servants and the criminal world are common phenomena resulting in breaches of trust, fraud, and other malpractices.

Finally, it can be said that white collar crimes can be carried out by people in every friendly class. White-collar crime is a sort of peaceful crime that is monetarily persuaded. White-collar crimes might be perpetrated by people or at a corporate level. Because of the complex innovation now accessible, in any case, even white-collar crimes perpetrated by an individual may bring about many millions in misfortunes for the victims.

Types of White Collar Crime

White-collar crimes are as hard to identify as they are not difficult to carry out. The detection systems on which police and government traditionally depend appear to be uniquely deficient for this immense new collection of crimes. Also, however people have learned through the ages to be careful about outsiders in the city, they have not yet figured out how to secure themselves against immense undertakings. A substantially more logical examination must be embraced on the causes, degree, and qualities of white-collar crimes before we can foster work-capable prevention methodologies [6]. Eight classes of white-collar offenses committed by people can be distinguished:

- Securities-related crimes.
- Bankruptcy fraud.
- Fraud against the government.
- Consumer fraud.
- Insurance fraud.
- Tax fraudbery, corruption, and political fraud.
- Insider-related fraud.

White Collar Crime V. Blue Collar Crime

There are a few contrasts between white-collar crimes and blue-collar crimes. Blue-collar crime (BCC) is a term used to depict crimes that are perpetrated principally by people who are from a lower social class. This is in contrast to white-collar crime, which alludes to a crime that is generally perpetrated by people from a higher social class. White collar crime is a crime perpetrated by a person of upper financial class throughout the occupation. On the other hand, BCC is a crime carried out under different reformatory laws [7]. Conventional crimes are more normal like attack, theft, dacoity, murder, assault; hijacking, and other demonstrations including brutality and so forth which are for the most part perpetrated by the under-favored class. On the other hand, the advantaged renowned class and enormous corporations are associated with white collar crimes. The criminal content, for example, *mensrea* or liable brain is a fundamental element of each traditional or blue collar crime. Numerous rules dealing with white collar crime don't need *mensrea* in the severe feeling of the term, yet precept of constructive *mensrea* applies in such cases. Another striking feature of white collar crime is that there is no current legislation in our country to prevent white collar crime. There are different sorts of penal statutes existing now in Bangladesh in various fields.

Despite the fact that individuals from the upper social layers are accepted to have uncorrupted social exercises, it has become realized that specific professions offer rewarding freedoms for criminal demonstrations, known as white-collar crimes, in which these persons have been included. The progression of business and innovation has made white-collar criminality a worldwide phenomenon. Of a relative multitude of variables, the economic and modern development all through the world has maybe been the most expected reason for expanding white-collar crimes lately. Remarking on the developing rate of white-collar crime in Bangladesh, the law commission in its twenty 10th reports saw that advanced logical and mechanical turns of events and monopolistic patterns in business the world has prompted a colossal expansion in white-collar crimes [8].

White Collar Crimes in Bangladesh: At a Glance

Bangladesh is not the out of survivor of white-collar crime, rather this sort of crime leads the country into a higher defiled country on the world. Bangladesh has followed other developing countries in an equivalent hold of white-collar criminality. The quick improvement in the economy and modern development in the ongoing many years has expanded white-collar crimes in the current day. Beforehand (during the time of BNP-Jamat govt.) the Transparency International Bangladesh (TIB) has recognized Bangladesh as the worst country on the planet for five continuous years. People of the upper financial class, administering elites, and people of various gatherings are perpetuating white-collar crimes in Bangladesh. They are making a lot of cash through defilement, manipulation and the abuse of power, causing severe detriment to the national economy. It is normal information that specific professions offer rewarding freedoms for criminal demonstrations and dishonest people in business, different professions, and even in open life [8]. Here the lawmakers who hold the force are for the most part criminalized and adulterated. The higher instructed people who sit in the higher situation of the administrative body submit various sorts of defilement. The business bunches take the risk and they additionally energize the officials and lawmakers to participate in debasement for their own shake. The callings of humankind, for example, Doctors, Engineers, Lawyers, NGO holders, Teachers are not out of this. That doesn't imply that all people in the posh are defiled and criminalized however the number of good people is not many.

The Causes of White Collar Crimes in Bangladesh

White-collar crimes can be committed for a couple of various reasons. They could be impacted by money, impacted by power. However, they are regularly non-violent offenses that are committed by somebody with some degree of advantage. There is, notwithstanding, more to understanding the brain science of a white-collar criminal than knowing why they perpetrate these offenses. In any case, which isolates them from other crimes is that it requires some degree of advantage. In contrast to thievery and attack (which can be committed by anybody), a white-collar crime (like theft and corporate extortion) must be committed on the off chance that somebody approaches certain monetary records and classified data. The principle justification perpetrating a white-collar crime is close to a home addition, which normally includes some sort of profit. Yet, on the off chance that you truly need to understand why people carry out these crimes, you need to understand the brain science that inspires them to overlook business morals and disregard the law [9].

As a general rule, the reasons for white-collar crime are economic trouble and ravenousness. There are other causes like the freedom to perpetrate crime, situational tension on the individual, and the issues relating to honesty. Numerous researchers then again accept that eagerness isn't the primary justification for white-collar crime, however, the inborn qualities of getting more than others are the fundamental driver of white-collar crime. Nonetheless, there are different explanations behind the white-collar crime, for example:

► Not actually, crimes: Some offenders persuade themselves that their activities are not actually crimes on the grounds that the demonstrations included don't look like road crimes. For instance, a drug specialist who etches

customers on doctor prescribed medications might defend her conduct by disclosing to herself that it doesn't actually hurt anybody.

▶ Not understandable/realizable: Some business people feel justified in perpetrating white-collar crimes since they accept that administration guideline doesn't actually understand the business world or their exercises or the issues of contending in the free venture framework.

▶ Ignorance of people: One of the main reasons for white-collar crime is the obliviousness of people about this crime. As the idea of the crime is totally not the same as customary crimes, people once in a while understand it however they are the most noticeably terrible casualties of such crime. The more mindfulness will increment among people the less will be the quantities of white-collar crime.

▶ For greediness: Rationalizing avarice is a typical characteristic of white-collar criminals. Some white-collar criminals accept that everybody disregards business laws, so it isn't the case terrible on the off chance that they do as such themselves. So, voracity is another inspiration for white-collar crime.

▶ Necessity: Greed is not the lone inspiration for white-collar crime, need additionally pays a significant job. Chief might temper with organization books since they want to keep or work on their positions, fulfill their personalities or backing their youngsters. Ladies indicted in lower-echelon positions and their demonstrations appear to be spurred more out of economic endurance than covetousness and power.

▶ For social and economic changes: the ascents of white-collar criminality in numerous countries have harmonized with the advancement made in those countries in the economic and mechanical fields. It is not really amazing that the two cycles ought to go together thinking about that a large portion of the white collar crimes are, straightforwardly or by implication, associated with the creation and circulation of abundance.

▶ Scientific and technological development: The advance of mechanical and logical improvement is adding to the rise of 'mass society', with an enormous majority and little controlling tip-top, empowering the development of restraining infrastructures, the ascent of an administrative class and complex institutional component. The powerlessness of all areas of society to appreciate in full this need brings about the rise and development of white collar and economic crimes.

Other than the above-examined causes, it is important to make reference to some other normal factors which are answerable for the commission of White Collar Crimes [10]:

- a) Economic and industrial growth.
- b) Socio-economic change in the society.
- c) Recent development of IT.
- d) Opportunities created by corporate culture.
- e) Family pressure.
- f) Lack of effective punishment.
- g) The passiveness of government.
- h) The lengthy and defective procedures of the courts etc.

White Collar Crime and Related Laws in Bangladesh

In the event of white-collar crimes there is different kind of disciplines recommended in various laws or Acts. It relies generally upon the current overall set of laws of a country. That implies which sort of crime is considered as white-collar crime or which sort of crime isn't considered as white-collar crime is absolutely subject to existing laws of the particular country. There are numerous such types of white-collar crimes continually occurring around us in which we are pretty much-becoming victims. A few crimes recorded above are discovered remediable in different laws however we barely get the benefits of these remedies. Since these crimes are generally perpetrated by the dignitary and compelling persons of the general public so the public authority associations aren't seen to eagerly make a legitimate and prompt move against them. After looking for insurance of law against them it is not really conceivable to remain against them. Among elites and predominant persons the individuals who are engaged with these crimes in the majority of cases, they can evade trial [11]. Despite the fact that they perpetrate crimes yet they are not distinguished as criminals for their financial and exceptionally respected condition in the general public. Indeed, even they haven't kept any proof of their crimes. So, the majority of the occasions, they stay past the restraint of law. For a moment it is said that burglary, theft, murder, assault, and so on kinds of crimes are unforgivable crimes perceived in our society. But when many people kicked the bucket in the article of clothing and mechanical plants for the carelessness of some dignitary or compelling

persons then it isn't considered as such intolerable crimes than the referenced previously. Yet, after a seemingly endless amount of many years, no preliminary has been executed or seen for such sorts of crimes.

Further, for the absence of appropriate mindfulness among the people about the law in regards to white-collar crime, the public interest isn't excessively strong against the white-collar criminals. These criminals are openly especially deferential to the law of the country. However, in down to earth their demeanor is resembling a dacoit to their greatest advantage. Absence of legitimate discipline, they perpetrate crimes again and again. The circumstance might appear to be that a few demonstrations are enacted in the state to save the compelling class and then again to abuse the more fragile class. Bangladesh has not yet authorized any direct provision for white-collar crime. It is given in another manner, however, no place is this crime straightforwardly referenced in the law of Bangladesh. Nonetheless, the Bangladesh Penal Code, 1860 does not unequivocally specify any crime or disciplined for such offenses as a white-collar crime or a man of his word's crime. In any case, there is no question that the individuals who perpetrate white-collar crimes are criminals [12]. There is no key or subjective distinction between common crime and white-collar crime; what exists is irrelevant and the contrast between the two is as far as law implementation. In the event that white-collar crime is brought to the level of a crime, it is feasible to rebuff white-collar criminals just as common crimes. Therefore, as well as instituting separate laws, it will be feasible to destroy such crimes from the general public if the political character of these criminals is eliminated and their resources are severely rebuffed through the development of exceptional councils. In far off nations, the court weighs numerous elements when choosing the sentence in a white-collar crime, which incorporates protections misrepresentation, theft, tax avoidance, and tax evasion. While the Code spells out maximums (two years less a day and a \$5,000 fine for misrepresentation underneath \$5,000 and a limit of 14 years in jail for extortion above \$5,000), in pretty much every white-collar crime the Crown will look for a sentence that incorporates imprisonment [13]. That is on the grounds that courts need to show they are viewing monetary crimes in a serious way and the possibility of detainment can stop others from comparable activities.

Bangladesh should likewise set explicit laws and disciplines like them. Miserable yet obvious, financial, political, social, geological, and mental reasons, different sorts of white-collar crime are expanding quickly in the country. Presently, in case there were severe laws against white-collar crime in our region, there would not be such countless white-collar crimes in Bangladesh. Laws are expected to draw out the appalling look taken cover behind a respectable look. The concerned authority of Bangladesh should make arrangements against these crimes as quickly as time permits and endorse discipline for these kinds of crimes.

Negative Impacts of White Collar Crimes in Different Sectors in Bangladesh

In Bangladesh white collar crimes, as opposed to blue-collar crimes, are on the ascent. Here politics has been criminalized and corruption politics has taken fortress. Transparency International (TI), a German-based organization has recognized previously Bangladesh as the most corrupt country in the world for sequential five years. People of upper financial class, administering elites, and people of various groups are perpetrating white-collar crimes. They are making a colossal measure of money by corruptions manipulation and abuse of power causing severe detriment to the national economy. Needless to say, such crimes committed by socio-economically superior people severely hamper the interests of society. Their crimes are inadequately centered, more often than not updated, and stay past the space of a legitimate cycle. They are exceptionally compelling as far as power and money [7]. Sad but true, economic, political, social, geographical, and psychological reasons, various types of white-collar crime are increasing rapidly in the country. These crimes are creating huge obstacles to national progress and development. These crimes are creating huge obstacles to national progress and development [14]. In Bangladesh not just the people of upper financial class are associated with white-collar crime, the people from top to bottom are rehearsing this bad habit, so far corruption, pay off and other misbehaviors are concerned. In distinguishing and examining white-collar crime in Bangladesh, all inescapable corruption has taken the premier need. White collar crimes are so destructive to society that they straightforwardly influence the monetary state of the country. A couple of impacts of such crimes are as under—

» Hazardous to Society: This crime has now become a threat to society. White collar criminality is a revile to society in light of the fact that such crimes not just put the country into an incredible monetary misfortune yet additionally aims fall in virtues [10].

» Crime against Society: It is really an offense of "treason". The techniques by which the assessments are dodged or dark money is skimmed in the market and so forth are such offenses, which are committed only for the individual additions at the expense of substantial misfortune to State.

» Economic Misbalance: At the point when a group of people having a place with rich and creative class, through their unlawful sources, acquire and more profit, the greater part class experiences the indecencies of it.

» Unfavorable Effect on Future Generation: When the entire economy of the country is upset by White Collar criminality, the group of people yet to come will experience the ill effects of destitution, joblessness.

» Misfortune to Government Revenues: When white-collar criminals sidestep duties or cover fewer charges, the entire financial strategy to the Government is upset.

» Effect on Society because of Hoarding: While the country is influenced by cataclysmic events like a flood, typhoon, draft, and additionally by the economic log jam or swelling, some of compelling political individual (particularly from the resistance) attempt to store colossal measure of every day vital merchandise. Thus, there is a counterfeit emergency of products on the lookout and the cost of merchandise eventually rises. In this way, because of that mal-practice, the general public is influenced in various manners thinking about an immense measure of monetary misfortune [15].

» Deception of Law: There are a few disciplines which are listed in the Penal Code, 1860 about accepting bribes and forgery. In any case, white-collar criminals steal a colossal measure of money through underhandedness or corruption. In any case, they are not rebuffed as expected. Since them don't feel that, they don't commit any offense whatsoever.

» Effect on Judicial Sector: Today, the criminal possess have their promoters who are generously compensated by the criminals and they lead criminals of general public to take off from the ambit of discipline by actuating the legal officers just as the Law Enforcing Agencies.

» Effect on Infrastructural Progress: In the development work of the public authority, more often than not a major measure of money is being stolen by the white-collar criminals. Thus, the interstate, multi-reason connect, and the public authority foundations are tumbling down before the timetable season of finishing. And the infrastructural progress of the country is reciprocal, getting destroyed.

» Effect on Parliamentary Budget: Through the report of GFI (Global Financial Integrities) somewhat recently, six needs centers of money are carried to other countries. In the event that this measure of money is discounted into the banks of our country, then the country will profit in a few different ways other than confronting a colossal measure of misfortune.

» Effect on Medical Sector: Most of the doctors allude to enthusiasm for different sorts of clinical trials in their set up indicative place and endorse medication of those organizations who give them increasingly more examples of medications at the same time and other offices. Every one of these is an instance of white-collar crimes however they are not unequivocally rebuffed because of the absence of appropriate laws.

» Effect of White Collar Crimes on Educational Sector: Educational sectors are getting destroyed step by step because of White Collar Crimes drastically. An immense monetary enrichment from different unfamiliar assets like HEG projects has been abused by the arrangement producer of the instructive service of the public authority. Therefore, the research sectors of the colleges do not profit appropriately. And the instructive arrangement of our country is deteriorating step by step.

Since these crimes are for the most part committed by the dignitary and powerful people of the general public so the public authority associations aren't seen to eagerly make an appropriate and quick move against them. In the majority of cases, these sorts of crimes don't disable us straightforwardly yet lethal influence our general public. These crimes are committed by such sorts of people who are socially, economically, and occupationally grounded just as compelling in the general public. Typically commoners can't make out these sorts of crimes. In spite of the fact that they can see the result of these crimes on them however for this situation, they sit around aimlessly. As they are stranded so they can't conflict with the activities of white collar criminals. In such a manner, these criminals are hesitant to assume their exercises as crimes. And to control these white collar crimes in Bangladesh a unique sanctioning is particularly critical to be passed by our sovereign law-making authority [14].

RECOMMENDATIONS

In a country like Bangladesh where huge scope of starvation, mass lack of education, and obliviousness influence the existence of the people, white collar crimes are bound to increase to an enormous extent. Control of these crimes is an urgent issue for the criminal equity organization in this country. Notwithstanding, a portion of the significant and critical proposals for fighting white collar criminality will be expressed as follows:-

- a) Making public awareness against these crimes through the media of press, stage and the other general media helps. Serious lawful education projects may maybe help in decreasing the frequency of white collar criminality to be a significant degree. Developing countries like Bangladesh are not yet aware of white-collar crimes, many in the general public do not yet know about this crime clearly. So, in order to stop this crime, to raise public awareness of this crime through various sources of media are needed.
- b) Extraordinary tribunals ought to be comprised with the ability to grant sentence to detainment up to the most elevated discipline under the Special Act. Some special tribunals need to be set up to give them the power to punish such offenders at any time, although the criminal is a high-class person in society. And it is important to make it clear that the law is the same for everyone and that no matter how high a class of people, no one can survive by committing a crime.
- c) Rigid administrative laws and extreme punishment for white collar criminals might help in lessening these crimes. Bangladesh has not yet made the most severe punishment for this crime. As a result, the upper-class people are still committing crimes without any hesitation and the amount of this type of crime is increasing day by day. Indeed, even enactments with review activity might be legitimized for this reason.
- d) A different section on white collar crimes and financial crimes ought to be joined in the Special Act by correcting the Code so that white collar criminals who are indicted by the court do no way out punishment on account of their high economic wellbeing.
- e) White collar wrongdoers ought to be managed harshly by endorsing stiffer punishments keeping in see, the gravity of injury caused to the general public as a result of these crimes. The Supreme Court, in *M. H. Haskot v. the State of Maharashtra*, in this setting noticed, "Soft sentencing justice is gross injustice where many innocents are the potential victims".
- f) There is an urgent requirement for a National Crime Commission which may solidly handle the issue of crime and criminality in the entirety of its aspects.
- g) Most importantly, public cautiousness is by all accounts foundation of hostile to white-collar crime strategy. Except if the white-collar crimes become despicable to the public psyche, it won't be feasible to contain the developing hazard. To achieve this target, there is a need for fortifying ethics especially, in the higher layers and among the public administrations. It is further important to advance sound group standards and administration morals dependent on the twin ideas of total trustworthiness and respectability for public government assistance. This is a potential through character working at the grass-roots level and uncalculating a feeling of genuine worry for the country among youths so they are ready and prepared for an upstanding living when they enter public life.
- h) Essential amendments ought to be made in existing laws. Because the laws of Bangladesh have not yet enacted this crime and the punishment for this crime. As a result, there is still no fear of the perpetrators being punished for their crimes and they are able to escape after committed their crimes. Therefore, the laws of Bangladesh should be amended as soon as possible to punish for this crime.
- i) Besides a different and unmistakable enactment ought to be passed by our public parliament. As white-collar crime is not a common crime, this crime is having a terrible effect on the country, the nation, and society. And the biggest thing is that they don't commit this crime for their poverty, they commit this crime for their greed. People from upper-class society commit this crime, not ordinary people. So, their punishments should be the most severe, that is why the strictest laws and punishments should be made.
- j) The principles and guidelines of the said order (assuming any) ought to be streamed and carried out by the court and Law Enforcing Agencies.
- k) In addition, a different and necessary section identifying with white collar criminality ought to be presented in the course educational program of the relative multitude of offices at the college level.

CONCLUSION

While reading an article if it is observed by a person shutting his eyes, imagine that he is not being seen by anyone. That doesn't mean, he isn't actually being seen by anyone? What which is exists won't be vanished or terminated only for the explanation that it isn't been perceived. In the same way, a white-collar criminal may not be absolved from criminal obligation simply for the explanation that he isn't been sentenced under the criminal law i.e., Code of Criminal Procedure, Penal Code, *Nari-O-ShishuNirjaton Damon Ain*, and so on Somewhat, white-collar criminals are more genuine, hazardous criminals than some other common criminals sentenced under the standard criminal laws. White-collar criminals are the machine of making the customary criminal. The white-collar criminal reasons the customary criminal to carry out crime to assist the white-collar criminals. Their crime affects others to perpetrate crime. They render the customary criminal. Accordingly, presently it is extremely evident that to diminish the crime from the world, it ought to be the premier obligation to announce the white-collar crimes as the crime and afterward to find vital ways to forestall and control the white-collar criminal. White collar crime incorporates an assortment of law infringement by people or groups that stand firm on critical footings in society, an infringement that can truly affect society. These criminals are freely particularly conscious of the law of the country. Be that as it may, in viable their disposition is resembling a dacoit to their greatest advantage. They commit crimes over and over again due to a lack of adequate discipline. White collar

crime is a serious financial crime, according to the findings of the investigation. Its ramifications and consequences on society are far more severe than those of blue collar crime. Indeed, even white collar criminals break the law on a regular basis to practice their power and money. Along these lines, there has become an urgent requirement for the government to enact particular legislation to deal with this major crime in the Bangladesh's best interests.

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